
4 **The core-mantle mode of gravitational oscillation**

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7 **Abstract** We present the characteristics of a mode of axial oscillation between Earth's
8 mantle, fluid core and solid inner core that has not been previously reported. The mode
9 involves a quasi-rigid rotation of the fluid core outside the tangent cylinder (TC) exchanging
10 its angular momentum with the mantle via a three step process. First, by a magnetic torque
11 with the fluid inside the TC; second by a magnetic torque between the latter and the inner
12 core; and finally by a gravitational torque between the inner core and mantle. Although
13 the gravitational torque is purely between the mantle and inner core, the mode involves an
14 oscillation of the whole of the core, and we refer to it as the core-mantle gravitational (CMG)
15 mode. This form of gravitational oscillation occurs when the magnetic field within the core is
16 sufficiently strong that the propagation time of Alfvén waves is shorter than the mode period,
17 which is the case for Earth. We show how the period, quality factor Q and structure of the
18 CMG mode depends on the strength of the gravitational torque and viscous relaxation time
19 τ_i of the inner core. For Earth, the CMG mode period should be in the range of 40 to 100
20 years, but viscous relaxation of the inner core likely implies a small Q , below 1 if $\tau_i < 10$
21 years. Our results suggest that the CMG mode may act to amplify resonantly, though only
22 modestly, multi-decadal changes in the length of day driven by zonal accelerations in the
23 fluid core.

24 **Non-technical summary** The Earth's mantle, fluid core and inner core are coupled by forces that allow for natural
25 modes of oscillations between them. Here, we describe a mode that we term the core-mantle gravitational mode,
26 or CMG mode for short. The mode is sustained by the gravitational torque between the inner core and mantle and
27 by the internal magnetic field that couples the inner core to the fluid core. We compute the period, the decay rate,

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and the structure of the motion in the fluid core for different sets of parameters. We show that, based on current estimates of the strength of the gravitational coupling, the period of the CMG mode should be in the range of 40 to 100 years. However, we also show that viscous relaxation of the inner core and electromagnetic friction at the core-mantle boundary attenuate the CMG mode rapidly. This suggests that it is unlikely that the CMG mode can account for a specific frequency in the spectrum of the observed decadal changes in the length of day. However, it is possible that the presence of the CMG mode may help to amplify resonantly, though only modestly, multi-decadal changes in the length of day driven by zonal accelerations in the fluid core.

1 Introduction

To first order, mantle convection on Earth is characterized by a circum-Pacific ring of cold, downwelling subducted plates separating two antipodal regions of upwelling, one under the Pacific ocean and the other under Africa (e.g. Defraigne et al., 1996; Simmons et al., 2007). This produces a mass anomaly primarily at spherical harmonic degree 2 order 2 reflected in the observed geoid at the surface (Hager et al., 1985). This mantle mass anomaly imposes a gravitational potential within the core, deforming the inner core boundary (ICB) topography into an equatorially elliptical shape (Buffett, 1996a). Because of the density contrast between the inner core and the fluid core, this ICB topography creates an additional mass anomaly.

If the inner core is axially rotated, an axial gravitational torque acts to restore the longitudinal alignment between the ICB and mantle mass anomalies. This torque provides the restoring force for a natural mode of axial oscillation (Buffett, 1996a) which has been referred to as the mantle-inner core gravitational (MICG) mode (Mound and Buffett, 2006). Electromagnetic (EM) coupling between the fluid and inner core at the ICB should be strong (e.g. Gubbins, 1981), and as a result the region of the fluid core inside the tangent cylinder (TC, i.e. the axial cylinder tangent to the equator of the inner core) is expected to be entrained into co-rotation with the inner core (Mound and Buffett, 2006). The period of the MICG mode depends on the amplitude of the degree 2 order 2 mantle mass anomalies (Buffett, 1996a; Davies et al., 2014; Chao, 2017; Shih and Chao, 2021) and is estimated to be in the range of of 7-18 years (Davies et al., 2014).

How the region of the fluid core outside the TC (ROTC) affects the MICG depends on the strength of the magnetic field within the core. At decadal periods, axisymmetric azimuthal (zonal) motion in the ROTC takes the form of rigidly rotating nested cylindrical surfaces (Jault, 2008). Adjacent cylinders are coupled by the magnetic field that threads their surfaces. This coupling allows for the propagation of Alfvén waves in the cylindrically radial direction and for normal modes of axial oscillations between cylinders referred to as torsional oscillations (TO, Braginsky, 1970). For a weak magnetic field of the order of 0.2-0.3 mT – once believed to be a representative strength within the core – the period of the fundamental mode of TO is in the range of 60-80 years (Zatman and Bloxham, 1997), much longer than the MICG mode period. The faster oscillations of the TC involved in the MICG mode launch Alfvén waves

60 in the ROTC that excite high harmonics of TO modes with short wavelengths, and large cancellations occur in the
61 axial angular momentum carried by the ROTC (Mound and Buffett, 2003). Consequently, when the magnetic field is
62 weak, the ROTC plays a limited role in the angular momentum dynamics of the MICG mode and the MICG period
63 is virtually identical to that computed under the assumption of fully decoupled ROTC (Mound and Buffett, 2003;
64 Mound and Buffett, 2006). However, for a magnetic field strength within the core of a few mT – as we now believe
65 to be the case (Gillet et al., 2010) – the period of the fundamental mode of TO is approximately 6 years. In this case,
66 the similar period of the MICG implies that the oscillating TC launches Alfvén waves that excite low harmonics of
67 TO modes with long wavelengths and the ROTC carries a significant net axial angular momentum (Dumberry, 2025,
68 henceforth referred-to as Paper 1). As a result, the oscillating motion of the TC involved in the MICG mode cannot
69 be decoupled from these TO modes. Indeed, Paper 1 showed that when Alfvén waves can readily traverse the width
70 of the core before they get attenuated, the MICG mode is no longer an individual mode of the coupled core-mantle
71 system; instead, it gets absorbed into the spectrum of TO modes.

72 However, as we shall show, a different mode of gravitational oscillation between the mantle and the core is possible
73 in a strong field regime. When the angular momentum of the core changes slowly compared to the propagation time
74 of Alfvén waves, the latter act to eliminate differential angular zonal motion in the ROTC. That is, the magnetic field
75 effectively locks the whole of the ROTC into a quasi-rigidly rotating body. It is then possible to have a global mode
76 of axial oscillation which involves an EM coupling at the TC between this rigidly rotating ROTC and the fluid region
77 inside the TC (RITC), an EM coupling between the RITC and the inner core at the ICB, and a gravitational coupling
78 between the inner core and mantle. Hence, a gravitational mode of oscillation between the mantle and inner core
79 remains possible, though one that involves the whole of the core instead of only the TC (see Figure 1a). Since the
80 moments of inertia of the inner core and the RITC are much smaller than that of the ROTC, the angular momentum
81 is conserved primarily through a balance between the oppositely oscillating ROTC and mantle. To distinguish this
82 mode from the MICG, we refer to it as the core-mantle gravitational (CMG) mode. As we show below, the period of
83 the CMG mode is longer than that of the MICG mode, in the multi-decadal range.

84 The objective of the present study is to present the characteristics of the CMG mode. As we describe below,
85 whether the inner core oscillates in sync with the ROTC or instead with the mantle depends on the relative strengths
86 of the gravitational coupling between the inner core and mantle versus the EM coupling between the RITC and ROTC.
87 When the EM coupling strength at the TC is much larger, the inner core follows the ROTC and entire core rotates
88 as a quasi-rigid body (Figure 1b); we refer to this limit as the rigid core regime. When instead it is the gravitational
89 coupling that is stronger, the motion of the inner core remains quasi-locked to the mantle (Figure 1c); we refer to this
90 limit as the locked inner core regime.

91 Our study is organized as follows. In section 2, we show how the CMG mode emerges from the angular momentum
92 equations of the core-mantle system. We present analytical expressions for its period and quality factor Q in both the
93 rigid core and locked inner core regimes. In section 3, we compute numerically the CMG mode and show how its

94 period and Q depend on the strength of the gravitational coupling factor between the inner core and mantle, the
 95 viscosity of the inner core and EM damping at the CMB. We conclude our study in section 4 with a geophysical
 96 discussion.

Figure 1: The angular velocity structure of the mantle (Ω_m orange arrows), fluid core (Ω_f blue arrows) and inner core (Ω_i red arrows) in (a) a generic case of the CMG mode, (b) the rigid core regime and (c) the locked inner core regime. The part of the fluid core overlapping the inner core represents the flow inside the TC. For ease of visualization, the relative angular velocity amplitudes and the radii of each regions are not drawn to scale.

97 2 Theory

98 2.1 The coupled core-mantle system of axial oscillations

99 Paper 1 presents a model that captures the coupled oscillations between the mantle, inner core (radius r_i) and fluid
 100 core (outer radius r_f) in the absence of an external torque. This coupled core-mantle system broadly follows that
 101 developed in several earlier studies (Buffett, 1996b; Buffett, 1998; Mound and Buffett, 2003; Mound and Buffett,
 102 2005; Dumberry and Mound, 2008; Dumberry and Mound, 2010). It includes TO modes in the fluid core, EM
 103 coupling at the ICB and CMB, and gravitational coupling between the mantle and inner core. The full development
 104 of the model will not be repeated here, but in order to extract the basic attributes of the CMG mode, it is convenient
 105 to reproduce the equations that govern its angular momentum dynamics.

106 We use C_m , C_i to denote the axial moments of inertia of the mantle and inner core, and Ω_m , Ω_i to denote the
 107 fluctuations of their angular velocities with respect to their mean rotation rates. Temporal changes in the axial angular
 108 momentum of the fluid core are carried by zonal flows in the form rigid cylindrical surfaces aligned with the rotation
 109 axis (e.g. Jault, 2008). We use cylindrical coordinates (s, ϕ, z) , so that a cylinder with a cylindrical radius s intersects
 110 the CMB at axial position $z_f = \sqrt{r_f^2 - s^2}$ in the Northern hemisphere. Cylinders inside the TC ($s < r_i$) intersect the
 111 ICB at $z_i = \sqrt{r_i^2 - s^2}$. We use $\Omega_f = \Omega_f(s)$ to denote the fluctuation of the angular velocity of a cylinder located at
 112 cylindrical radius s with axial moment of inertia density

$$c_f = 4\pi\rho s^3(z_f - z_i), \quad (1)$$

114 where ρ is the density and where $z_i = 0$ for $s > r_i$.

115 The axial angular momentum equations for the mantle and inner core are given, respectively, by

$$116 \quad C_m \frac{d\Omega_m}{dt} = \bar{\Gamma}\alpha + \int_0^{r_f} \mathcal{F}_m [\Omega_f - \Omega_m] ds, \quad (2a)$$

$$117 \quad C_i \frac{d\Omega_i}{dt} = -\bar{\Gamma}\alpha + \int_0^{r_i} \mathcal{F}_i [\Omega_f - \Omega_i] ds, \quad (2b)$$

118 where $\bar{\Gamma}$ captures the strength of the gravitational coupling between the mantle and inner core and α is the longitudinal
119 angle of misalignment between the degree 2 order 2 mantle density field and ICB topography. The evolution of α is
120 given by

$$121 \quad \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \Omega_i - \Omega_m - \frac{\alpha}{\tau_i}, \quad (2c)$$

122 where τ_i is the viscous relaxation time of the inner core assuming a Maxwell rheology. The parameters \mathcal{F}_m and \mathcal{F}_i
123 capture the strength of the torques from all surface forces acting on the mantle at the CMB and on the inner core at
124 the ICB, respectively. We assume that \mathcal{F}_m and \mathcal{F}_i result from electromagnetic (EM) coupling as specified by eqs. (5a)
125 and (5b) of Paper 1.

126 The fluctuations in Ω_f of individual cylinders in the fluid core are governed by

$$127 \quad c_f \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\rho\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(c_f \frac{\{B_s b_\phi\}}{s} \right) - \mathcal{F}_m [\Omega_f - \Omega_m] - \mathcal{F}_i [\Omega_f - \Omega_i] + \nu \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(c_f \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial s} \right), \quad (3a)$$

128 where μ is the magnetic permeability, ν is the kinematic viscosity, B_s is the s -component of the background mag-
129 netic field, and $\{\cdot\}$ denotes an average over a cylindrical surface. The variable b_ϕ is the azimuthal magnetic field
130 perturbation induced by the differential motion of the cylinders, and obeys

$$131 \quad \frac{\partial b_\phi}{\partial t} = s B_s \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial s} + \eta (\nabla^2 \mathbf{b})_\phi, \quad (3b)$$

132 where $\eta = 1/\mu\sigma$ is the magnetic diffusivity.

133 We use a simplified one-dimensional (1D) model of B_s which is only a function of s . For this simplified model,
134 B_s is equal to its rms strength over a cylinder; $B_s = \{B_s\}$. In this case, eqs. (3a) and (3b) can be written as

$$135 \quad c_f \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\rho\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(c_f \frac{\{B_s\} b_\phi}{s} \right) - \mathcal{F}_m [\Omega_f - \Omega_m] - \mathcal{F}_i [\Omega_f - \Omega_i] + \nu \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(c_f \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial s} \right), \quad (4a)$$

$$136 \quad \frac{\partial b_\phi}{\partial t} = s \{B_s\} \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial s} + \eta \left(\frac{\partial^2 b_\phi}{\partial s^2} + \frac{1}{s} \frac{\partial b_\phi}{\partial s} - \frac{b_\phi}{s^2} \right), \quad (4b)$$

138 where b_ϕ now represents the azimuthal perturbation of the magnetic field averaged over a cylindrical surface. These
139 corresponds to Eqs. (10) and (11) of paper 1, which capture the leading order angular momentum dynamics of
140 magnetically coupled cylinders in the core. This simplified system, however, underestimates the magnetic diffusion

141 of a three-dimensional (3D) \mathbf{b} -field induced by the shear of a fully 3D B_s -field by a rigid flow. As we will show, the
 142 CMG mode features a core flow with small gradients in s (at least in the rigid core regime) which should minimize
 143 magnetic diffusion. In this sense, the salient features of the CMG mode should be properly captured with this 1D
 144 model.

145 Eqs. (4a) and (4b) require boundary conditions at $s = 0$ and $s = r_f$. At $s = 0$, we impose the regularity conditions
 146 $d\Omega_f/ds = 0$ and $b_\phi = 0$. At $s = r_f$, we set $d\Omega_f/ds = 0$, which implies no viscous torque at the CMB, and b_ϕ is set
 147 by the magnetic field perturbation resulting from EM coupling (eq. 16 of Paper 1).

148 2.2 The core-mantle gravitational mode

149 Let us now show how the CMG mode emerges from the above system. The CMG mode can be broadly described as
 150 an axial oscillation between the mantle, inner core, and the quasi-rigid RITC and ROTC. Let us define the moments
 151 of inertia of the RITC and ROTC, respectively C_{fi} and C_{fo} , as

$$152 \quad C_{fi} = \int_0^{r_i} c_f ds, \quad (5a)$$

$$153 \quad C_{fo} = \int_{r_i}^{r_f} c_f ds. \quad (5b)$$

154 Let us further introduce the mean angular velocities inside and outside the TC, respectively Ω_{fi} and Ω_{fo} , defined
 155 such that

$$156 \quad \int_0^{r_i} c_f \Omega_f(s) ds = C_{fi} \Omega_{fi}, \quad (6a)$$

$$157 \quad \int_{r_i}^{r_f} c_f \Omega_f(s) ds = C_{fo} \Omega_{fo}. \quad (6b)$$

158 By this construction, Ω_{fi} and Ω_{fo} carry all the angular momentum of the core. For periodic oscillations between Ω_i ,
 159 Ω_m , Ω_{fi} and Ω_{fo} about a mean rotation rate, conservation of angular momentum in the absence of an external torque
 160 is expressed as

$$161 \quad C_i \Omega_i + C_{fi} \Omega_{fi} + C_{fo} \Omega_{fo} + C_m \Omega_m = 0. \quad (7)$$

162 A necessary condition for the CMG mode is a strong internal magnetic field, in which case EM coupling at both the
 163 ICB and the TC should be strong. This implies that Ω_i and Ω_{fi} should not be much larger than Ω_{fo} . However, since
 164 $C_i, C_{fi} \ll C_{fo}$, to first order, the angular momentum balance in the CMG mode is primarily between the mantle and
 165 the ROTC,

$$166 \quad C_{fo} \Omega_{fo} \approx -C_m \Omega_m. \quad (8)$$

167 Evolution equations for Ω_{fi} and Ω_{fo} can be formed by integrating eq. (3a) from $s = 0$ to r_i and from $s = r_i$ to
 168 r_f , respectively. Taking the time derivative of each of the resulting equations, inserting eq. (3b), and neglecting both

169 magnetic diffusion within the core and EM coupling at the CMB, yields

$$170 \quad C_{fi} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{fi}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\{B_s^2\}}{\rho\mu} \left(c_f \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial s} \right) \Big|_{s=r_i} - \int_0^{r_i} \mathcal{F}_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\Omega_f - \Omega_i] ds - \int_0^{r_i} \mathcal{F}_m \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\Omega_f - \Omega_m] ds, \quad (9a)$$

$$171 \quad C_{fo} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{fo}}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{\{B_s^2\}}{\rho\mu} \left(c_f \frac{\partial \Omega_f}{\partial s} \right) \Big|_{s=r_i} - \int_{r_i}^{r_f} \mathcal{F}_m \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\Omega_f - \Omega_m] ds. \quad (9b)$$

172 As eq. (9b) shows, in the absence of coupling at the CMB, a change in the net angular momentum of the ROTC can
173 only occur as a result of a Lorentz torque at the TC. The equal and opposite torque applies on the RITC.

174 The combination of eqs. (2a)-(2c) and eqs. (9a)-(9b) captures the coupled oscillations between the mantle, inner
175 core, RITC and ROTC that defines the CMG mode. It involves three torques of restoring nature: the gravitational
176 torque between the inner core and mantle; the Lorentz torque at the TC between the RITC and ROTC, and the EM
177 torque at the ICB between the inner core and the RITC. The latter (through \mathcal{F}_i) includes also a dissipative part, and
178 EM coupling at the CMB and viscous relaxation of the inner core also contribute to dissipating the mode energy.

179 Building an analytical prediction of the period and decay rate of the CMG mode as a function of model parameters
180 is not straightforward because $\{B_s^2\}$, \mathcal{F}_i and \mathcal{F}_m all vary with s , and the profile of $\Omega_f(s)$ is expected to change with
181 the phase of the mode. Our chief objective, instead, is to identify the key factors controlling the oscillating dynamics
182 of the CMG mode. For this purpose, we can prescribe a simple form of $\Omega_f(s)$. For oscillation periods much longer
183 than the travel time of Alfvén waves, the latter should act to redistribute any local change in angular velocity toward a
184 mean profile of $\Omega_f(s)$ as a function of s . This profile should approach Ω_i near $s = 0$ (because of the expected strong
185 EM coupling at the ICB) and approach Ω_{fo} in the ROTC. Let us write

$$186 \quad \Omega_f(s) = \Omega_i + f(s)(\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i). \quad (10)$$

187 The function $f(s)$ should tend to zero as $s \rightarrow 0$ and approach 1 in the ROTC. $f(s)$ is time-dependent, but the form of
188 eq. (10) is sufficiently general to capture the profile of Ω_f in the CMG mode.

189 EM coupling at the CMB and viscous inner core relaxation act to dissipate the energy of the CMG mode. Their
190 effects are important, as we show in our results. However, to further understand the dynamics of the CMG mode, we
191 want first to focus on the factors that contribute to sustaining it. For this purpose, let us assume no EM coupling at the
192 CMB ($\mathcal{F}_m \rightarrow 0$) and a rigid inner core ($\tau_i \rightarrow \infty$). Using $\Omega_f(s)$ from eq. (10) in eqs. (2a)-(2c) and eqs. (9a)-(9b), we

193 obtain the following coupled system:

$$194 \quad C_m \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_m}{\partial t^2} = \bar{\Gamma} [\Omega_i - \Omega_m], \quad (11a)$$

$$195 \quad C_i \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_i}{\partial t^2} = -\bar{\Gamma} [\Omega_i - \Omega_m] + \mathcal{K}_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i], \quad (11b)$$

$$196 \quad C_{fi} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{fi}}{\partial t^2} = \Gamma_{tc} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i] - \mathcal{K}_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i], \quad (11c)$$

$$197 \quad C_{fo} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{fo}}{\partial t^2} = -\Gamma_{tc} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i], \quad (11d)$$

198 where

$$199 \quad \Gamma_{tc} = 4\pi r_i^3 \sqrt{r_f^2 - r_i^2} \left(\frac{\{B_s^2\}}{\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial s} \right) \Big|_{s=r_i}, \quad (12a)$$

$$200 \quad \mathcal{K}_i = \int_0^{r_i} \mathcal{F}_i f(s) ds. \quad (12b)$$

201 This simplified system captures the essential ingredients of the CMG mode. The frequency of the CMG mode
 202 and the relative phase of each of the four regions depend on $\bar{\Gamma}$, Γ_{tc} and \mathcal{K}_i . At leading order, the CMG mode is an
 203 exchange of angular momentum between the mantle and the ROTC (see eq. 8) so Ω_m and Ω_{fo} should oscillate in
 204 phase but in opposite direction. The leading order dynamics of the CMG mode can thus be illuminated by forming an
 205 equation for the differential angular velocity $\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_m$. We build this equation by multiplying eqs. (11d) and (11a)
 206 by C_m and C_{fo} , respectively, and subtracting the two resulting equations. This gives,

$$207 \quad C_m C_{fo} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_m] = -\bar{\Gamma} [\Omega_i - \Omega_m] - \Gamma_{tc} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i]. \quad (13)$$

208 The two torques on the right-hand side depend on Ω_i . Whether Ω_i tends to follow Ω_m or Ω_{fo} more closely, or remains
 209 somewhere in between Ω_m and Ω_{fo} , depends on the relative strengths between $\bar{\Gamma}$ and Γ_{tc} . A stronger $\bar{\Gamma}$ acts to bring
 210 Ω_i into co-rotation with Ω_m , whereas a stronger Γ_{tc} acts instead to limit the differential rotation between Ω_{fo} and Ω_{fi} ,
 211 and thus also Ω_i since it is tied to Ω_{fi} by EM coupling at the ICB. This competition between $\bar{\Gamma}$ and Γ_{tc} determines
 212 the phase of Ω_i and also the frequency of the CMG mode.

213 It is then useful to explore two end-member limits based on the relative coupling strengths between $\bar{\Gamma}$ and Γ_{tc} .
 214 To give an indication of the expected strength of Γ_{tc} , taking $\{B_s\} = 3$ mT, and approximating $\partial f / \partial s \sim 1/r_i$, gives
 215 $\Gamma_{tc} \approx 4 \times 10^{20}$ N m. When $\bar{\Gamma} \ll \Gamma_{tc}$, the strong EM coupling at the TC acts to limit the difference between Ω_{fo} and
 216 Ω_{fi} (and thus Ω_i). In this case, the whole of the core rotates as a quasi-rigid body, Ω_i is in phase with Ω_{fo} and their
 217 amplitudes are similar. This is the rigid core regime (Figure 1b). Because $\Omega_{fo} \approx \Omega_i$, the frequency of the CMG mode
 218 is proportional to $\sqrt{\bar{\Gamma}}$ (see eq. 13). When $\bar{\Gamma} \gg \Gamma_{tc}$, Ω_i is instead locked to Ω_m by the strong gravitational coupling
 219 between the inner core and mantle. Since Ω_{fo} is oscillating in the opposite direction as Ω_m , the contrast between Ω_{fo}
 220 and Ω_i is maximized, and the frequency of the CMG mode should then be proportional to $\sqrt{\Gamma_{tc}}$ (see eq. 13); this is

221 the locked inner core regime (Figure 1c). We further explore each of these two limits in the next two subsections.

222 2.3 The rigid core regime

223 In the limit when $\bar{\Gamma} \ll \Gamma_{tc}$, then $\Omega_{fo} \approx \Omega_i \approx \Omega_{fi}$; the whole of the core rotates as a quasi-rigid body. Let us denote
224 the mean angular velocity of this quasi-rigid core by Ω_c . The CMG mode dynamics is captured by eq. (11a) and an
225 equation formed by summing eqs. (11b), (11c) and (11d),

$$226 \quad C_m \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_m}{\partial t^2} = \bar{\Gamma} [\Omega_c - \Omega_m], \quad (14a)$$

$$227 \quad C_c \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_c}{\partial t^2} = -\bar{\Gamma} [\Omega_c - \Omega_m], \quad (14b)$$

228 where $C_c = C_{fo} + C_{fi} + C_i$ is the moment of inertia of the whole of the core. Setting Ω_m and Ω_c proportional to
229 $\exp(-i\omega_o t)$, the undamped frequency ω_o of the CMG mode in this limit is

$$230 \quad \omega_o = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\Gamma} C}{C_m C_c}}, \quad (15)$$

231 with $C = C_m + C_c$ the moment of inertia of the whole Earth. Even though the gravitational torque that sustains the
232 oscillation is purely between the mantle and inner core, the strong EM coupling at both the ICB and the TC entrains
233 the whole of the fluid core into co-rotation with the inner core. In this limit, the CMG mode is analogous to the MICG
234 mode except that it involves the whole of the core.

235 The small differential rotation at the ICB implies a weak rate of dissipation by EM coupling at the ICB. Dissipation
236 in the rigid core regime may be dominated by EM coupling at the CMB and by the viscous relaxation of the inner core.
237 To re-introduce their influence, we form a coupled system by combining eq. (2a) and an equation formed by adding
238 eq. (2b) to eq. (4a) integrated from $s = 0$ to r_f , with the approximation $\Omega_f = \Omega_i = \Omega_c$,

$$239 \quad C_m \frac{d}{dt} \Omega_m = \bar{\Gamma} \alpha + \mathcal{K}_m [\Omega_c - \Omega_m], \quad (16a)$$

$$240 \quad C_c \frac{d}{dt} \Omega_c = -\bar{\Gamma} \alpha - \mathcal{K}_m [\Omega_c - \Omega_m], \quad (16b)$$

241 where

$$242 \quad \mathcal{K}_m = \int_0^{r_f} \mathcal{F}_m ds. \quad (17)$$

243 Taking $C_c(d/dt + 1/\tau_i)$ of eq. (16a), $C_m(d/dt + 1/\tau_i)$ of eq. (16b), substituting eq. (2c), and subtracting the
244 two resulting equations, we form a damped harmonic oscillator equation for the differential angular velocity $\Delta\Omega =$
245 $\Omega_c - \Omega_m$,

$$246 \quad \frac{d^2 \Delta\Omega}{dt^2} = -\left(\omega_o^2 + \frac{1}{\tau_i \tau_m}\right) \Delta\Omega - \left(\frac{1}{\tau_i} + \frac{1}{\tau_m}\right) \frac{d\Delta\Omega}{dt}, \quad (18)$$

247 where τ_m is a timescale of attenuation due to EM damping at the CMB given by

$$248 \quad \tau_m = \frac{C_m C_c}{\mathcal{K}_m C}. \quad (19)$$

249 Setting $\Delta\Omega$ proportional to $\exp(-i\omega t - \lambda t)$, the frequency ω , decay rate λ and quality factor (Q) of the CMG mode in
250 the rigid core regime are

$$251 \quad \omega = \omega_o \left(1 - \left(\frac{\tau_i - \tau_m}{2\omega_o \tau_i \tau_m} \right)^2 \right)^{1/2}, \quad (20a)$$

$$252 \quad \lambda = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\tau_i + \tau_m}{\tau_i \tau_m}, \quad (20b)$$

$$253 \quad Q = \frac{\omega}{2\lambda} = \left(\left(\frac{\tau_i \tau_m \omega_o}{\tau_i + \tau_m} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\tau_i - \tau_m}{\tau_i + \tau_m} \right)^2 \right)^{1/2}. \quad (20c)$$

254 It may appear paradoxical that the frequency depends solely on $\bar{\Gamma}$ given that the rigid core regime applies when
255 $\bar{\Gamma} \ll \Gamma_{tc}$. The reason is that since the strong magnetic field locks the whole of the core into a rigid rotation, the
256 magnetic torques at the TC and ICB are much weaker than the gravitational torque between the mantle and inner core.

257 To give a numerical example of a typical CMG mode period in this regime, let us take the values of C_m and C_c in
258 Table 1, $\tau_i \rightarrow \infty$, $\tau_m \rightarrow \infty$, and $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{19}$ N m; this gives an undamped CMG period of 182 yr. The criteria for $Q > 1$,
259 and hence for a CMG mode that is not overdamped, is that the attenuation timescale τ formed by

$$260 \quad \frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{1}{\tau_m} + \frac{1}{\tau_i}, \quad (21)$$

261 should be longer than $1/\omega = T/2\pi$ where T is the mode period. To continue the example above, for a CMG mode
262 with a period of ~ 180 yr, $Q > 1$ requires that τ_i and τ_m be both longer than 30 yr.

263 **2.4 The locked inner core regime**

264 In the limit when $\bar{\Gamma} \gg \Gamma_{tc}$, the inner core is locked to the motion of the mantle, so $\Omega_i = \Omega_m$. The CMG mode in
265 this limit is dominated by the oscillation between the RITC and ROTC of eqs. (11c) and (11d). The dynamics of the
266 ROTC can be retrieved from eq. (11d) and an equation formed by adding eqs. (11c) and (11d), using $C_{fi} \ll C_{fo}$ and
267 setting $\Omega_i = \Omega_m$:

$$268 \quad C_{fo} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{fo}}{\partial t^2} = -\Gamma_{tc} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_m], \quad (22a)$$

$$269 \quad C_{fo} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{fo}}{\partial t^2} = -\mathcal{K}_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_m]. \quad (22b)$$

270 Using $\Omega_m/\Omega_{fo} = -C_{fo}/C_m$ from eq. (8), and setting Ω_{fo} and Ω_m proportional to $\exp(-i\omega t - \lambda t)$ gives the following
 271 predictions for ω , λ and Q :

$$272 \quad \omega^2 = \frac{\Gamma_{tc}}{C_{fo}} \left(1 + \frac{C_{fo}}{C_m} \right), \quad (23a)$$

$$273 \quad \lambda = \frac{Re[\mathcal{K}_i]}{C_{fo}} \left(1 + \frac{C_{fo}}{C_m} \right), \quad (23b)$$

$$274 \quad Q = \frac{\omega}{2\lambda} = \frac{\sqrt{\Gamma_{tc} C_{fo} C_m}}{2Re[\mathcal{K}_i] \sqrt{C_{fo} + C_m}}. \quad (23c)$$

275 These predictions depend on Γ_{tc} and \mathcal{K}_i , which in turn depend on $\{B_s\}$ at the TC and on the profile of $\Omega_f(s)$. For the
 276 purpose of computing estimates of ω , λ and Q , let us assume a simple profile based on eq. (10) with $f(s)$ given by
 277 the following sinusoidal function,

$$278 \quad f(s) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{r_i} (s - r_i) \right) \right], \quad \frac{r_i}{2} < s < \frac{3r_i}{2}, \quad (24a)$$

$$279 \quad f(s) = 0, \quad s < \frac{r_i}{2}, \quad (24b)$$

$$280 \quad f(s) = 1, \quad s > \frac{3r_i}{2}. \quad (24c)$$

281 For this profile, $\partial f/\partial s$ at the TC is equal to $\frac{1}{2}\pi/r_i$, and taking a representative $\{B_s\} = 3$ mT at the TC gives $\Gamma_{tc} =$
 282 6.87×10^{20} N m. Using C_m and C_{fo} from Table 1, this gives a period of 21.7 yr. Using this period to compute the
 283 magnetic skin depth at the ICB, on which \mathcal{F}_i depends (see eqs. 5-6 of paper 1), and integrating the product of \mathcal{F}_i
 284 and $f(s)$ inside the TC (eq. 12b) gives $Re[\mathcal{K}_i] = 1.99 \times 10^{28}$ kg m² s⁻¹, which gives $Q = 1.88$. These estimates of
 285 the period and Q are crude as they entirely depend on our assumed choice of $f(s)$. The true profile of $f(s)$ differs
 286 from this simple function, depends on the choice of model parameters and also varies with the phase of the mode.
 287 Nevertheless, we will show that these estimates of ω and Q are correct in an order of magnitude sense. Note also that
 288 the frequency in the locked inner core regime is independent of $\bar{\Gamma}$; this is expected since $\bar{\Gamma}$ is sufficiently strong to
 289 lock the mantle and inner core into co-rotation.

290 EM coupling at the CMB is not included in eqs. (22a)-(22b) but further contributes to attenuate the CMG mode.
 291 Also note that since the inner core and mantle are locked into co-rotation, α (the angle of longitudinal misalignment,
 292 eq. 2c) remains small and viscous inner core relaxation is then not an important source of dissipation in the locked
 293 inner core regime.

294 **3 Results**

295 **3.1 The CMG mode in the spectrum of modes**

296 We now compute the free modes of axial oscillations of the coupled system of eqs. (2a-2c) and eqs. (4a-4b). These
 297 are found using the same numerical technique as described in Paper 1. We assume that each variable has a time-

298 dependency of the form $\exp(-i\omega t)$, so the system can be cast as an eigenvalue problem with eigenvalues ω cor-
 299 responding to the complex frequencies of the free modes. Solutions depend on the chosen profile of $\{B_s\}$ in the
 300 core and on the models of EM coupling at the CMB and ICB. We use the same EM coupling models with the same
 301 numerical values as in Paper 1. We also use the same $\{B_s\}$ profile, given by

$$302 \quad \{B_s\} = \bar{B}_s \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{r_f}\right) + \left(\frac{s}{r_f}\right) \langle B_{r,m} \rangle, \quad (25)$$

303 with $\bar{B}_s = 3.3$ mT and $\langle B_{r,m} \rangle = 0.319$ mT, with the latter representing the rms strength of the total radial field at the
 304 CMB. A summary of all the numerical parameters used to produce our results is given in Table 1.

305 EM coupling at the ICB depends on the magnetic skin depth $\delta = \sqrt{2\eta/|\omega|}$, which depends on the frequency. The
 306 modes that we compute are obtained using the following procedure. First, we set δ based on a value of $\omega = 2\pi/6$
 307 yr^{-1} so that the first few harmonics of TO modes are computed approximately correctly for our assumed \bar{B}_s . The
 308 CMG mode though has a lower frequency. To improve its accuracy, we use an iterative procedure, updating δ with the
 309 frequency of the CMG mode found at the previous iteration. Convergence is achieved after three or four iterations.

Table 1: Parameters used in calculations of the normal modes.

Parameter	value
radius of the core	$r_f = 3.480 \times 10^6$ m
radius of the inner core	$r_i = 0.35r_f = 1.218 \times 10^6$ m
moment of inertia, mantle	$C_m = 7.13 \times 10^{37}$ kg m ²
moment of inertia, inner core	$C_i = 5.87 \times 10^{34}$ kg m ²
moment of inertia, RITC	$C_{fi} = 2.06 \times 10^{35}$ kg m ² (*)
moment of inertia, ROTC	$C_{fo} = 9.22 \times 10^{36}$ kg m ² (*)
moment of inertia, whole core	$C_c = 9.48 \times 10^{36}$ kg m ² (*)
moment of inertia, whole Earth	$C = 8.08 \times 10^{37}$ kg m ² (*)
uniform density, fluid core	$\rho = 1.1 \times 10^4$ kg m ⁻³
conductivity, core	$\sigma = 10^6$ S m ⁻¹
magnetic diffusivity, core	$\eta = \frac{1}{\mu\sigma} = 0.796$ m ² s ⁻¹
kinematic viscosity, fluid core	$\nu = \frac{\eta}{100} = 0.00796$ m ² s ⁻¹
s-magnetic field amplitude, fluid core	$\bar{B}_s = 3.3$ mT
rms radial magnetic field, CMB	$\langle B_{r,m} \rangle = 0.319$ mT
axial dipole, CMB	$B_m^d = 0.391$ mT
axial dipole, ICB	$B_i^d = 3.0$ mT or 6 mT

(*) Based on a uniform fluid core density of $\rho = 1.1 \times 10^4$ kg m⁻³.

310 For our first set of results, we use a dipole field amplitude at the ICB of $B_i^d = 3$ mT, a viscous relaxation time for
 311 the inner core of $\tau_i = 1000$ yr, and a mantle conductance of $G_m = 10^5$ S. The latter choice gives an EM attenuation time
 312 of $\tau_m = 17100$ years. Although both τ_i and τ_m are unrealistically high for Earth, our first objective is to demonstrate
 313 that the characteristics of the CMG mode are captured by the simplified system of eqs. (11a)-(11d) when the main
 314 source of dissipation is from EM coupling at the ICB. More realistic choices of τ_i and τ_m are investigated further
 315 below.

316 Figure 2 shows the frequency and decay rate of a subset of modes computed for three different choices of the

317 gravitational strength factor: $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{19}$ N m (green circles), $\bar{\Gamma} = 3 \times 10^{20}$ N m (red triangles) and $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{23}$ N m (blue
 318 squares). In each case, the spectrum of modes includes a set of TO modes with a first harmonic that has a period of
 319 approximately 6 years (frequency ~ 1 yr $^{-1}$). We also find a mode that has a lower frequency; this corresponds to the
 320 CMG mode. In increasing order of $\bar{\Gamma}$, the periods are 184.9 yr, 42.6 yr and 26.1 yr and the Q values are 21.7, 5.76
 321 and 2.30.

Figure 2: Frequency and decay rate of a subset of the normal modes computed with $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{19}$ N m (green circles), $\bar{\Gamma} = 3 \times 10^{20}$ N m (red triangles) and $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{23}$ N m (blue squares). Full symbols denote TO modes, open symbols denote the CMG modes.

322 Figure 3 shows the real and imaginary parts of Ω_i , Ω_m and the profiles $\Omega_f(s)$ of the CMG modes of Figure 2. In
 323 each case, the phase is chosen such that the real part of Ω_m (thick grey line) is maximum in the retrograde direction
 324 and the amplitude is normalized such that the mean angular velocity of the whole core $\Omega_c (= -\Omega_m \cdot (C_m/C_c))$ is set
 325 equal to 1. The imaginary part (panel b) is equivalent to the solution obtained a quarter of a cycle later (i.e. with a
 326 phase delay of $\pi/2$.) The profile obtained with $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{19}$ N m illustrates a case when the CMG mode is in the rigid
 327 core regime; the inner core follows the motion of the ROTC and the whole core oscillates as a quasi-rigid body. In
 328 contrast, the profile with $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{23}$ N m corresponds with a CMG mode in the locked inner core regime; the motion of
 329 the inner core is gravitationally locked to the mantle and oscillates in the opposite direction to the ROTC. The profile
 330 obtained with $\bar{\Gamma} = 3 \times 10^{20}$ N m captures a case in between these two asymptotic regimes, with the inner core pulled
 331 approximately equally by the gravitational torque and by the Lorentz torque at the TC (via EM coupling at the ICB).
 332 For each choice of $\bar{\Gamma}$, the profile of $\Omega_f(s)$ matches Ω_i near $s = 0$ and its mean value in the ROTC is approximately
 333 equal to the mean motion of the whole core. At the phase of the mode when the difference between Ω_m and Ω_{fo}
 334 is maximum (panel a), the profile of $\Omega_f(s)$ is consistent with the form of eq. (10), although this profile is time-
 335 dependent. These solutions also illustrate how the fast propagating Alfvén waves in the fluid core act to eliminate
 336 large gradients in $\Omega_f(s)$ outside the TC on the longer timescale of the CMG mode; the whole of the ROTC oscillates
 337 as a quasi-rigid body. Note the large differential velocity between $\Omega_f(s)$ and Ω_i in the cylindrical radius range of
 338 $0.1 < s/r_f < 0.35$; this causes significant EM damping at the ICB (through \mathcal{K}_i).

Figure 3: (a) Real and (b) imaginary part of the angular velocity structure as a function of cylindrical radius (s/r_f) for the CMG mode computed with $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{19}$ N m (green line for Ω_f , thick light green line for Ω_i), $\bar{\Gamma} = 3 \times 10^{20}$ N m (red lines for Ω_f , thick orange line for Ω_i) and $\bar{\Gamma} = 10^{23}$ N m (dark blue line for Ω_f , thick light blue line for Ω_i). For each choice of $\bar{\Gamma}$, the phase corresponds to when the real part of Ω_m (thick grey line) is maximum in the retrograde direction (the imaginary part of Ω_m is equal to zero at that phase). Amplitudes are normalized such that the mean angular velocity of the rigid core $\Omega_c = -\Omega_m \cdot (C_m/C_c)$ is equal to 1.

3.2 The period and Q of the CMG mode

Figure 4 shows how the period and Q of the CMG mode change with $\bar{\Gamma}$ based on the same values of $B_i^d = 3$ mT, $\tau_i = 1000$ yr, and $G_m = 10^5$ S used in the previous subsection. When $\bar{\Gamma} < 10^{20}$ N m, the CMG mode is in the rigid core regime, its period (Figure 4a) is longer than 70 years and is proportional to $(\bar{\Gamma})^{1/2}$. The period matches very well the prediction from eq. (20a). When $\bar{\Gamma} > 10^{22}$ N m, the CMG mode is in the locked inner core regime and its period is fixed at 26.1 yr, independent of $\bar{\Gamma}$, in general good agreement with the prediction of 24.6 yr based on eq. (23a) with $f(s)$ approximated as eq. (24a). The boundaries of the rigid core and locked inner core regimes are, of course, not precisely defined and the choices adopted on Figure 4 are only meant as a representative guide.

For $\tau_m, \tau_i \rightarrow \infty$, the dynamics of the CMG mode is captured by the reduced system of eqs. (11a)-(11d). A prediction for its frequency can be built from eq. (11d):

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\Gamma_{tc}}{C_{fo}} \frac{(\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i)}{\Omega_{fo}}. \quad (26)$$

Figure 4: (a) Period and (b) Q of the CMG mode (blue circles) as function $\bar{\Gamma}$. Light blue lines show the predicted periods and Q based on eqs. (26) and (27), respectively. Red lines show the predictions in the rigid core regime based on eqs. (20a) and (20c). Orange lines show the predictions in the locked inner core regime based on eqs. (23a) and (23c). The pink and blue shaded areas highlight the rigid core and locked inner core regimes, respectively.

350 To first order, ω depends on $\sqrt{\Gamma_{tc}}$ and on the contrast between Ω_{fo} and Ω_i ; a larger contrast leads to a faster frequency.

351 We show on Figure 4a the predicted period computed from eq. (26), with Γ_{tc} (eq. 12a) evaluated from the actual
 352 $\Omega_f(s)$ profile of the CMG mode solution. The very good match, for all values of $\bar{\Gamma}$, confirms that the the period of the
 353 CMG mode is always consistent with the Lorentz torque at the TC between the RITC and ROTC. When the RITC is
 354 almost co-rotating with the ROTC (rigid core regime), the stretching of the $\{B_s\}$ -field is minimal, the Lorentz torque
 355 at the TC is weak, and the CMG period is long. As $\bar{\Gamma}$ is increased, the gravitational pull on the inner core by the
 356 mantle is stronger, increasing the differential rotation and the Lorentz torque at the TC, resulting in a shorter CMG
 357 mode period. When the differential rotation at the TC is maximized, in the locked inner core regime, the Lorentz
 358 torque and CMG period no longer change with increasing $\bar{\Gamma}$.

359 Figure 4b shows how Q changes as a function of $\bar{\Gamma}$. Q increases with $\bar{\Gamma}$ in the rigid core regime, reaching a
 360 maximum of approximately 22 at $\bar{\Gamma} \approx 10^{19}$ N m, then decreases with $\bar{\Gamma}$ before settling to a value of 2.3 in the locked
 361 inner core regime. We also show on Figure 4b the predictions of Q from eq. (20c) in the rigid core regime and from
 362 eq. (23c) in the locked inner core regime. Both provide reasonable fits to the computed vales of Q . We can build a
 363 prediction of the decay rate λ valid for all values of $\bar{\Gamma}$ (when $\tau_m, \tau_i \rightarrow \infty$) by adding eqs. (11c) and (11d) and using

364 $C_{fi} \ll C_{fo}$,

365
$$\lambda = \frac{\mathcal{K}_i}{C_{fo}} \frac{(\Omega_{fo} - \Omega_i)}{\Omega_{fo}}, \quad (27)$$

366 with \mathcal{K}_i computed with the actual profile of $\Omega_f(s)$. The prediction of $Q = \omega/2\lambda$ based on this decay rate and ω from
 367 eq. (26) is shown in Figure 4b; it provides a good match to our computed values. This confirms that – when τ_i and
 368 τ_m are long – EM damping at the ICB regulates the dissipation of the CMG mode. In the rigid core regime, EM
 369 damping at the ICB is minimal since the inner core co-rotates with the RITC, and the prediction from eq. (27) is not
 370 as accurate. At the lowest values of $\bar{\Gamma}$, attenuation is instead primary from the combination of τ_i and τ_m , even for the
 371 large values that we have used in Figure 4b, and Q matches better the prediction of eq. (20c). Although τ_i and τ_m are
 372 fixed, the increase in period with decreasing $\bar{\Gamma}$ implies a lower Q as $\bar{\Gamma}$ gets smaller.

373 While the choices $\tau_i = 1000$ years and $G_m = 10^5$ S are useful to demonstrate the main properties of the CMG
 374 mode, they are not geophysically realistic. The viscous relaxation time of the inner core is likely much smaller than a
 375 1000 years given that the temperature at the ICB is at the melting point. Likewise, a more realistic mantle conductance
 376 is of the order of $G_m = 7 \times 10^6$ S (Kuvshinov et al., 2021), but it can be higher if there is a thin layer of iron-enriched
 377 material at the base of the mantle (Ohta et al., 2012; Ohta et al., 2014; Ho et al., 2024). Figure 5 shows how Q of the
 378 CMG mode varies with $\bar{\Gamma}$ for different choices of mantle conductance ($G_m = 7 \times 10^6$ S and 5×10^7 S, corresponding to
 379 $\tau_m = 244$ yr and 34 yr, respectively), inner core viscous relaxation times ($\tau_i = 100$ yr, 30 yr and 10 yr) and dipole field
 380 amplitude at the ICB ($B_i^d = 3$ mT and 6 mT). The high value of $B_i^d = 6$ mT for the dipole field amplitude at the ICB
 381 is not necessarily realistic, but it is used here to illustrate how a stronger radial field results in a tighter EM coupling
 382 at the ICB, and thus a weaker EM dissipation and a larger Q .

383 Lower values of τ_i and τ_m increase the decay rate and lead to a lower Q . Depending on the specific choices of
 384 G_m , τ_i and B_i^d , Q values on Figure 5 range between 0 and 7. Smaller values of τ_i and larger values of G_m (smaller
 385 τ_m) lead to a smaller Q , as expected. A larger B_i^d leads to larger Q . In the rigid core regime ($\bar{\Gamma} < 10^{20}$ N m), Q is
 386 independent of B_i^d as the inner core co-rotates with the fluid core and EM dissipation at the ICB is minimized. For
 387 $\bar{\Gamma} < 10^{19}$ N m, Q is small (typically below 1) because the period of the CMG mode is long compared to τ_i and τ_m . In
 388 the locked inner core regime ($\bar{\Gamma} > 10^{22}$ N m), Q is independent of τ_i (as expected), but depends on EM dissipation at
 389 both the CMB (a larger G_m leads to a smaller Q) and the ICB (a weaker $B_i^d = 3$ leads to a smaller Q). So long as Q
 390 is of order 1 or larger, the period of the CMG mode is not significantly altered from those shown in Figure 4a.

391 4 Discussion and conclusions

392 We have presented the attributes of an axial mode of oscillation of the coupled core-mantle system sustained by
 393 the gravitational torque between the mantle and inner core which we have termed the CMG mode. In contrast to
 394 the MICG mode, which involves an oscillation between the mantle and inner core (whether entraining or not the fluid
 395 region inside the TC), the CMG mode involves the whole of the core. It consists in an exchange of angular momentum
 396 primarily between the mantle and the fluid region outside the TC, with the latter oscillating quasi-rigidly as a result
 397 of strong internal magnetic coupling. The core-mantle exchange of angular momentum occurs through a set of three
 398 internal torques. First, the fluid outside the TC transmits angular momentum to the fluid region inside the TC by a

Figure 5: Q of the CMG mode as function $\bar{\Gamma}$ for a mantle conductance of (a) $G_m = 7 \times 10^6$ S and (b) $G_m = 5 \times 10^7$ S, different choices of viscous relaxation time ($\tau_i = 100$ yr, red squares; $\tau_i = 30$ yr, orange triangles; $\tau_i = 10$ yr, blue circles), and different dipole field amplitude at the ICB (full symbols, $B_i^d = 3$ mT; empty symbols, $B_i^d = 6$ mT). Values of $Q = 0$ indicate cases where the CMG mode was not found. The pink and blue shaded areas highlight the rigid core and locked inner core regimes, respectively. The dashed horizontal line marks $Q = 1$.

399 magnetic torque. Second, the fluid inside the TC transmits angular momentum to the inner core by EM coupling at
 400 the ICB. Finally, the inner core transmits angular momentum to the mantle by a gravitational torque. This form of
 401 gravitational oscillation, involving the whole of the core instead of only the inner core, occurs when the magnetic field
 402 within the core is sufficiently strong that the propagation time of Alfvén waves is shorter than the mode period, which
 403 is the case for Earth.

404 The behaviour of the inner core differs in the CMG and MICG modes. In the MICG mode the angular velocity
 405 of the inner core is opposite that of the mantle, and larger by a factor $C_m / (C_i + C_{fi})$. In the CMG mode, the motion
 406 of the inner core depends on the relative strengths between $\bar{\Gamma}$ and Γ_{tc} . When $\bar{\Gamma} \ll \Gamma_{tc}$, the strong magnetic coupling
 407 at the TC entrains the fluid inside the TC and the inner core into co-rotation with the fluid outside the TC. The whole
 408 of the core oscillates as a quasi-rigid body (the rigid core regime) so the angular velocity of the inner core is opposite
 409 that of the mantle, just as in the MICG mode, however its amplitude is smaller (approximately equal to C_m / C_c that
 410 of the mantle). When $\bar{\Gamma} \gg \Gamma_{tc}$, the strong gravitational coupling instead locks the inner core into a co-rotation with
 411 the mantle (the locked inner core regime). The behaviour of the inner core is in between these two asymptotic cases
 412 when $\bar{\Gamma}$ is of the same order of magnitude as Γ_{tc} .

413 For Earth, assuming a magnetic field $\{B_s\}$ inside the core of approximately 3 mT (Gillet et al., 2010) as we have
 414 used, and for the range of $\bar{\Gamma} = [0.3 - 2] \times 10^{20}$ N m estimated by Davies et al. (2014), the CMG mode period should

415 be in the range of 40-100 years (Figure 4a), either in, or at the edge of, the rigid core regime. The dissipation from
416 EM damping at the ICB, by itself, should lead to a Q in the range of 5 to 20 (Figure 4b). However, EM damping at the
417 CMB and viscous relaxation of the inner core likely reduce Q to lower values. For a mantle conductance of 7×10^6
418 S, based on the mantle conductivity model of Kuvshinov et al. (2021), and a rms radial magnetic field strength at the
419 CMB of 0.4 mT, the EM attenuation time at the CMB should be of the order of $\tau_m \approx 250$ yr. Yet, EM damping at
420 the CMB may be more significant. Several studies have shown that (Mg,Fe)O becomes highly conducting ($10^4 - 10^5$
421 S/m) in the lowermost mantle (e.g. Ohta et al., 2012; Ohta et al., 2014; Ho et al., 2024) and a thin (1 to 2 km) layer of
422 such iron-enriched material at the base of the mantle is supported by normal mode seismology (Russell et al., 2023).
423 Indeed, the presence of such a layer provides the conductance required to explain (by EM damping) the observed
424 dissipation in Earth's nutations (e.g. Buffett, 1992; Buffett et al., 2002; Koot et al., 2010; Koot and Dumberry, 2013),
425 and the observed attenuation of Alfvén waves (Gillet et al., 2010; Gillet et al., 2017). With a higher conductance
426 of 5×10^7 S, $\tau_m \approx 34$ yr, and the CMG mode should then be rapidly attenuated. In addition, viscous relaxation of
427 the inner core also acts to attenuate the CMG mode. As we have shown (Figure 5b), with a mantle conductance of
428 5×10^7 S, and for $\bar{\Gamma} = [0.3 - 2] \times 10^{20}$ N m, the viscous relaxation time of the inner core τ_i has to be longer than 10
429 yr for $Q > 1$. Using the mapping provided by Buffett (1997), this corresponds to an inner core viscosity of 5×10^{17}
430 Pa s. The viscosity of the inner core is not well known, but inferences from seismic analyses suggest that the inner
431 core topography deforms on a relatively short time, which implies a viscosity in this range (Vidale et al., 2025). To
432 summarize, the attenuation from both EM coupling at the CMB and viscous relaxation of the inner core implies that
433 if Q is above 1, it is likely not significantly larger than 1.

434 Given its low expected Q , it is then unlikely that a freely oscillating CMG mode is responsible for any specific
435 frequency in the spectrum of the observed decadal fluctuations in the length of day (LOD) (e.g. Roberts et al., 2007).
436 These decadal LOD changes are caused by forced zonal accelerations in the fluid core driven by convection (e.g. More
437 and Dumberry, 2018; Schwaiger et al., 2024; Aubert, 2026). The CMG mode may provide a resonant amplification
438 to the zonal accelerations in the core that have a timescale in the multi-decadal range, but this amplification is likely
439 modest at best given its expected low Q .

440 One limitation of our study is the assumption of axially invariant flow in the fluid core. Oscillations involving axial
441 flow gradients are possible in the form of Magnetic-Coriolis (MC) modes (Dumberry et al., 2025). Even though the
442 low harmonics of axisymmetric MC modes have longer periods, of the order of a thousand years, the flow structure in
443 the CMG mode may be modified by these MC modes in such a way that some departure from axial rigidity may occur
444 at periods of 50 to 100 years. Indeed, EM coupling at the ICB may trigger such axisymmetric MC waves (Dumberry
445 and Buffett, 1999), which may then alter the effective strength of this coupling, and also affect the attenuation of the
446 CMG mode. It is thus imperative that the attributes of the CMG mode should be confirmed with a more general model
447 of zonal core flows. In addition, if the top of the core is stratified, with a buoyancy frequency approximately equal to
448 Earth's rotation rate, free oscillations in the form of Magnetic-Archimedean-Coriolis (MAC) modes may have periods

449 in the same multi-decadal range as the CMG mode (Buffett, 2014; Buffett et al., 2016). It is then possible that MAC
450 modes interact with the CMG mode, although a dedicated study on this topic is required to understand the precise
451 form of this interaction.

452 Finally, even though our study has been anchored to Earth, the ideas of the CMG mode apply in a general sense
453 to any planetary body that has an inner core at its centre and a strong magnetic field permeating its core.

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456 using the GMT software (Wessel et al., 2013).

457 **Data availability**

458 Codes to reproduce all numerical experiments are freely accessible at the following data repository: [Dumberry \(2026\)](#).

459 **Competing interests**

460 The author of this paper has no competing interests.

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